

ASSESSMENT OF INDICATORS OF CYTOPENIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS OF VIRUS ETIOLOGY

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Significance. In the world, special attention is being paid to scientific research aimed at identifying changes in the general blood analysis in liver cirrhosis of viral etiology, as well as the characteristics of cytopenic syndrome and improving measures to develop these changes. In this regard, the study of the etiological factors of liver cirrhosis, that is, the study of the molecular genetic characteristics of the hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV), the identification of the pathogenetic development of the disease in patients with liver cirrhosis, the assessment of the level of features of cytopenic syndrome in these patients and their study of various stages of liver diseases and their relationship with etiology, early diagnosis of these changes and improvement of treatment requires implementation of a number of tasks, and conducting research in this direction is of particular importance.

The purpose of the study. Assessment of indicators of cytopenic syndrome during general blood analysis in patients diagnosed with liver cirrhosis of viral etiology.

Research material and methods. Scientific research work was carried out in 2023-2024 at the clinical base of the Tashkent Medical Academy and the Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical Medical Center of Epidemiology, Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (RSSPMCEMID). To carry out scientific research, patients were observed in the department of hepatology of the TMA clinic and the department of chronic viral hepatitis of RSSPMCEMID. A total of 60 patients with liver cirrhosis (B, C, D) of viral etiology were studied in the study. In the study group 45% of the patients were women and 55% were men. If we divide the patients by age, 31.6% of patients aged 20 to 40, 35% of patients aged 41 to 55, 56 to 75 and patients under the age of 33.4%. The tactics of clinical and laboratory examination, diagnosis and treatment of patients were carried out on the basis of the "Protocol on diagnosis and treatment of infectious diseases" of

the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Order 542 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

When laboratory tests were performed on patients, general blood analysis was taken from all patients from the first day of arrival to the hospital. These analyzes were checked in the hospital laboratory by conventional methods.

Results. According to the results of the research, the general blood analysis of 60 patients with viral hepatitis was studied. As a result, the decrease in blood cells was clearly evident: the erythrocyte index was found to be decreased in 24 (40%) of 60 patients, increased in 8 (13.3%) patients, and normal in 28 (46.7%) patients. The number of leukocytes decreased in 37 (61.7%) of 60 patients, increased in 5 (8.3%) patients, and remained unchanged in 18 (30%) patients. It was found that the thrombocyte index decreased sharply in 34 (56.6%) patients, and significantly increased in 3 (5.0%) patients. It was found that the amount of hemoglobin decreased in 29 (48.3%) patients, but the amount of hemoglobin was normal in 31 (51.6%) patients. ESR indicator in the general blood analysis was within the normal range in 33 (55.0%) patients, and in the remaining 27 (45%) patients, ESR was increased, and in these patients, new type of anemia, leukopenia and thrombocytopenia were clearly demonstrated.

Conclusions. A low level of hemoglobin in peripheral blood and low levels of blood cells (erythrocytes, leukocytes, platelets), an increase in ESR in most patients, as well as leukopenia and thrombocytopenia observed in all examined individuals indicate the presence of cytopenic syndrome in patients with liver cirrhosis of viral etiology.

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